

FDTD Models of Electromagnetic Scattering by the Human Body

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Abstract

We present simulations using the Finite Difference Time Domain (FDTD) technique on a highly detailed model of the human body. The emphasis is on radar scattering phenomenology, with results presented as Radar Cross Section (RCS) and Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) images.

I. Introduction

During the 1990's, concerns about the health effects of electromagnetic radiation within the wireless industry prompted a number of studies on the propagation of electromagnetic waves in the presence of a human body [1]. The Finite Difference Time Domain (FDTD) method [1, 2] was the natural candidate to modeling this type of problems, given the complexity of human tissues dielectric properties. However, most of these studies were oriented towards computing the radiation absorption rates inside the human body. More recently, the focus on military and national security applications has shown great potential for microwave radars in detecting the human presence in concealed environments. The main advantage of relatively low frequency radar is the ability of penetrating building structures (through-the-wall sensing), while offering reasonable resolution, especially when used in Ultra-Wideband (UWB) and Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) configurations. Scattering models of the human body are very useful in designing and predicting the performance of such radar systems. The purpose of this paper is to demonstrate utilizing the FDTD technique for simulating this type of applications, with emphasis on scattering phenomenology and issues related to the FDTD algorithm.

II. Algorithm and Problem Setup

For this application we used the three-dimensional FDTD algorithm developed at the Army Research Laboratory. It is a fully scalable code, designed to run on several High Performance Computing (HPC) platforms. The simulations presented here were all run at the Army Major Shared Resource Center (MSRC) in Aberdeen, MD.

We also used the human body model available on the web at the US Air Force Research Laboratory, RF Radiation Branch site. This site stores highly detailed FDTD-compatible grids, where the dielectric properties of each human tissues are sampled using 1 mm, 2 mm or 3 mm cubic cells. The complex permittivities of

tissues are given as parametric functions of frequency. However, our FDTD code handles only materials with constant (real part-) permittivity and conductivity over frequency, so we had to compute these values at the central frequency of our simulations. The effect of this approximation on the human body RCS will be discussed later.

For the 3 mm grid, the computational domain size was $236 \times 154 \times 666$ cells. Since we are interested in RCS-type calculations, the sources and receivers are assumed in the far field. The depression angle is always zero degrees (\mathbf{k} vector in the x - y plane), the human is placed in free-space and we always consider a monostatic radar configuration. The excitation pulse is Rayleigh 4th order, with a central frequency of either 1 GHz or 3 GHz, which is representative for UWB microwave radar. Its 3 dB band extends from about $0.5f_c$ to $2f_c$ (where f_c is the central frequency). We also performed simulations on the 2 mm grid, for which the computational domain size was $333 \times 210 \times 979$ cells. The 3 mm grid can be handled by one processor; for the 2 mm grid we needed 8 processors on each run.

In order to build SAR images, we used the time-domain FDTD-computed signatures at different azimuth angles. We employed the backprojection algorithm [3], with an integration angle of 40° . At 1 GHz central frequency, the approximate resolution is 20 cm in down-range and 20 cm in cross-range.

III. Results

We considered front (broadside) incidence in Fig. 1, both V-V and H-H polarizations, with 1 GHz central frequency excitation and the 3 mm grid. As one can notice, the two polarizations yield very similar RCS. One important question is whether the 3 mm cell size is fine enough to accurately represent the electromagnetic wave propagation through the human body. At 1 GHz and 3 mm cell size, the spatial sampling rate is 100 in free-space. However, some tissues in the human body have very high relative permittivity (in the 40-60 range), which makes the effective sampling rate within those media much smaller than in free-space. In order to assess the frequency limit where the RCS results on the 3 mm grid become inaccurate, we ran the same simulations on a 2 mm grid, over the 0-9 GHz band. The results, shown in Fig. 2 (V-V polarization only), indicate that the match is reasonably good up to 5 GHz, but the 3 mm grid may be inadequate for simulations above this frequency.

Another question we tried to answer was how much the penetration of electromagnetic radiation through the human body had an influence on the RCS. In Fig. 3 we compared the RCS of the 'real' model to that of a man made of a uniform material with dielectric properties close to the skin (V-V polarization). At $\epsilon_r = 50$, $\sigma = 1$ S/m, this material acts almost as a perfect reflector, so penetration in this case should not play a significant role in the RCS. Looking at the two graphs, we concluded that, except for low frequencies (up to 1.2 GHz), the penetration through the body is not important in RCS calculations. However, as

expected, the lower frequencies do penetrate the thin layer of skin and hit a relatively low dielectric/loss fat tissue, bouncing back and creating interference.

With regard to the constant permittivity/conductivity limitation of the FDTD code, we ran a simple test to evaluate its impact on our models. First, we utilized the permittivity and conductivity computed at 1 GHz (from the original data), then we ran the same simulation again with the material properties computed at 3 GHz. The results are shown in Fig. 4 and clearly prove that, except around 1 GHz, there is no difference between the two calculations. This is consistent with the previous paragraph conclusion, since the reflection coefficient of the skin is not expected to vary much with frequency. However, the differences around 1 GHz (where we have some penetration through the body) suggest that using constant ϵ and σ , computed at 1 GHz, is acceptable over a wide band of frequencies.

SAR images can offer more insight with regard to the scattering phenomenology than simple RCS plots. In Fig. 5 we depict the image obtained using a 1-GHz-centered pulse and 40° integration angle (H-H polarization). This represents a top view (with the man facing down the page) and the intensity scale in dBsm. One can notice the main scattering center (dark red) in the middle of the image, corresponding to the abdomen and chest of the human. In order to understand where the late-time feature came from, we removed different parts of the body (e.g., the head, or the legs), and re-ran the simulation. It turned out that removing the legs had the most dramatic effect in suppressing the late-time response, as shown in the image in Fig. 6. Our conclusion was that some kind of surface wave is excited along the body, and then re-radiated at the tips of different body parts.

IV. Conclusions

This paper presented simulation results on electromagnetic scattering from the human body. We analyzed different issues related to the FDTD algorithm that was used in this study and tried to infer some important phenomenological aspects by looking at RCS plots and SAR images. It should be mentioned that we only considered one human body model, available to us in a format compatible with the FDTD grid. Although different human bodies (leaner, shorter etc.) may display different radar scattering characteristics, we think that the conclusions formulated above are representative to any human body types.

References

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Fig. 1. RCS of the human body, front (broadside) incidence, 3 mm grid.

Fig. 2. RCS of the human body, front (broadside) incidence. Comparison between 2 and 3 mm grid models.

Fig. 3. RCS of the human body, front (broadside) incidence. Comparison between the real model and a uniform dielectric model.

Fig. 4. RCS of the human body, front (broadside) incidence. The effect of frequency-dependent permittivities on the RCS.

Fig. 5. SAR image of a complete human body, top view.

Fig. 6. SAR image of a human body with the legs removed, top view.